

Research and Applications

GALAXY CRUISE: User characteristics and their evolution in Japan's first big data-driven citizen science project in astronomy

Kumiko Usuda-Sato¹, Junko Shibata², Masayuki Tanaka¹, Michitaro Koike¹,
Seiichiro Naito¹, Hitoshi Yamaoka¹, Makoto Ando¹, Kei Ito³

¹National Astronomical Observatory of Japan, ²Japan Society for the Promotion of Science, ³The Cosmic Dawn Center

GALAXY CRUISE is the first Japanese online citizen science project in astronomy using big data. It is conducted by the National Astronomical Observatory of Japan (NAOJ) using large datasets collected by the Subaru Telescope near the summit of Maunakea, Hawai'i. Citizen astronomers classify and identify interacting galaxies on a PC or tablet. The Japanese and English Season 1 sites were launched on 1 November 2019 and 19 February 2020, respectively. Season 1 was completed in April 2022, and we are now in the final phase of Season 2, featuring fainter galaxies. In July 2021, we conducted a user questionnaire in Japanese and English, receiving 245 valid responses. We compared the reasons users indicated for participating in GALAXY CRUISE in the questionnaire with those they selected when registering. In this comparison, we found that the primary motivation for active users is to contribute to astronomy research both when registered and in the questionnaire, and they added more reasons as they continued to participate. The questionnaire results also show that active users have evolved their characteristics into authentic astronomy enthusiasts; they came to spend more time in astronomy and developed an interest for academic astronomy content. In this article, we will present the unique features of this project, the analysis of the user questionnaire, and our latest activities.

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Tasis Kapodistrias

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Aniket Sule

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Corresponding Author

Kumiko Usuda-Sato
kumiko.usuda@nao.ac.jp

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1. Introduction: Citizen Science in Astronomy

The Oxford English Dictionary defines “citizen science” as “scientific work undertaken by members of the general public, often in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists and scientific institutions” (Marshall et al., 2015). Even before the term came into use in the 1990s, citizen science was popular among the astronomy community. With their telescopes and other equipment, amateur astronomers have played a crucial role in discovering new objects, including asteroids, comets, and supernovae. Since the late 2000s, a new type of citizen science project has become active. Instead of direct observations, non-professionals (hereafter referred to as

citizen astronomers) access and classify large-scale observational data online. For example, Galaxy Zoo (e.g., [Lintott et al., 2008](#)), a project launched in 2007 in which citizen astronomers classify galaxy images from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS), has become one of the most successful citizen science projects and has evolved into the Zooniverse ([Simpson et al., 2014](#)) citizen science platform.

Previous studies ([Raddick et al., 2010](#); [Raddick et al., 2013](#)) have explored the motivations of citizen astronomers to spend their time and energy on their voluntary work in the early Galaxy Zoo projects. The studies revealed that the most common primary motivation for participation was to contribute to original scientific research, regardless of gender, age group, or educational level. The motivations and engagement patterns of participants in a similar citizen science project, CosmoQuest, were also investigated through interviews with citizen astronomers ([Gugliucci et al., 2021](#)). So-called “persisters”, who participate regularly, were found to have both intrinsic motivations (e.g., “interest in the subject”) and extrinsic motivations (e.g., “help out” for participation), whereas “dabblers”, who engage in the project sporadically, were found to have mainly extrinsic motivations for participating.

Though we use the term “citizen science” in this article to maintain consistency with previous leading papers, we note that it is also referred to as “community science” or “participatory science” to be inclusive of non-citizens ([Dance, 2022](#)).

2. Unique features of GALAXY CRUISE

The Subaru Telescope is an optical-infrared telescope operated by the National Astronomical Observatory of Japan (NAOJ) near the summit of Maunakea on the Island of Hawai'i. It has an 8.2-metre primary mirror, one of the world's largest monolithic mirrors. Hyper Suprime-Cam (HSC), the giant imaging camera mounted at the telescope's prime focus, has 870 million pixels and offers an ultra-wide field of view equivalent to nine full moons at optical wavelengths. For over seven years, starting in March 2014, the extensive observing programme called “Hyper Suprime-Cam Subaru Strategic Program (HSC-SSP)” was conducted for more than 330 nights. Its first, second, and third datasets were released to the public in February 2017 ([Aihara et al., 2018](#)), May 2019 ([Aihara et al., 2019](#)), and August 2021 ([Aihara et al., 2022](#)), respectively.

Many interacting and merging galaxies have been captured in HSC data. This class of galaxies is unique because their shapes are affected by complex gravitational interactions. Identifying these galaxies, classifying their shapes, and counting their numbers can help us unlock the secrets of galaxy evolution and understand the diversity of galaxies. However, it is challenging for researchers to conduct such studies independently due to the vast number of galaxies found in the cosmic images.

GALAXY CRUISE is the first online citizen science project conducted by NAOJ that encourages the Japanese general public to participate. It uses the second HSC-SSP dataset, released in

May 2019 and includes 3.8 years of data, corresponding to 174 nights of observation ([Aihara et al., 2019](#); [Usuda-Sato et al., 2021](#)). Citizen astronomers access the GALAXY CRUISE website¹ and classify galaxies. The Season 1 Japanese site launched on 1 November 2019, and the English site launched on 19 February 2020. In April 2022, we completed Season 1 with more than 2.6 million classification results for a pre-selected set of 21,587 galaxies, and began Season 2 with another set of 32,690 galaxies, most of which are fainter than those of Season 1.

We conducted the “2023 Special Campaign” from 12 September 2023 to 1 April 2024 (during Season 2) in response to a high-priority request from the GALAXY CRUISE science team in which citizen astronomers classified simulated galaxies from the Illustris TNG Project². These images were processed to be indistinguishable from real galaxies captured by the Subaru Telescope. The Special Campaign resulted in more than 400,000 classifications of 7,117 galaxy images. As of 1 August 2025, we have collected nearly 2.8 million classification results for Season 2 galaxies, reaching our goal of collecting at least 50 classification results for each galaxy. As the final phase of Season 2 before closing this project, we are now promoting the “Final Campaign” from 1 August to 31 October 2025.

The first scientific paper was published in October 2023 ([Tanaka et al., 2023](#)) and analysed the Season 1 classification results. With the high-quality images captured by the Subaru

Figure 1 Violent mergers identified by GALAXY CRUISE citizen astronomers. The galaxies are significantly distorted by strong tidal gravitational fields, demonstrating how violent mergers can be. Credit: NAOJ

Telescope and the high-accuracy classification results by citizen astronomers, we discovered many spiral galaxies previously identified as elliptical galaxies and interacting and merging galaxies that were not found to have interacting features in previous studies. In addition, citizen astronomers identified galaxies that are currently undergoing violent mergers. As shown in [Figure 1](#), this type of merger is characterised by significantly distorted shapes and very complex structures. Such violent mergers are extremely rare, and a statistical sample of such galaxies illustrates the power of visual classifications by many citizen astronomers. The second paper was published in January 2024 ([Shimakawa et al., 2024](#)). With the synergy between citizen astronomer classifications and artificial intelligence, 400,000 spiral galaxies and 30,000 ring galaxies were discovered in the third HSC-SSP dataset.

2.1 The GALAXY CRUISE website

2.1.1 Feature 1: Three steps of the easy-to-understand training menu Before citizen astronomers register to begin classification, they must complete training sessions to gain a basic understanding of galaxies. Unlike English-speaking countries, Japan had relatively few online citizen science projects, and we needed to provide simple but effective steps for citizen science beginners to become familiar with interacting galaxies and feel comfortable participating. During the planning phase, we found that many astronomy enthusiasts were intrigued by the programme, but were concerned that they should not participate if they had no prior or professional knowledge of galaxies. In response, we developed a detailed training menu with three steps to help citizen astronomers classify with confidence. With the support and guidance of the National Museum of Emerging Science and Innovation (Miraikan) in Tokyo, we spent almost a year developing the training menu with public experiments. First, we held face-to-face events at the museum, where we gave introductory lectures, allowing them to classify galaxies, and checked the accuracy rate. After that, we set up a touchscreen in the museum's exhibition hall where visitors could read the explanations and classify galaxies by themselves. We improved the menu contents based on the results, and the final version was published on the GALAXY CRUISE website. In addition to the training menu, the Practice Course is also available on the classification screen, allowing citizen astronomers to compare their classification results with those of the Captain, a galaxy researcher based at NAOJ.

2.1.2 Feature 2: voyaging-themed world and gamification events Our project is likened to a cruise ship in which many crew members sail together in the vast cosmic ocean. We created a cruise map, or the nautical chart, which represents GALAXY CRUISE's worldview from the observation map of HSC-SSP, with four "towns" (small and deep observation fields) and six "continents" (wide fields) for Season 1. When citizen astronomers completed a location, a departure stamp was added to the passport. Locations were divided into multiple areas, and participants could collect souvenirs (commemorative illustrations) upon completing certain areas. On each citizen astronomer's classification screen ([Figure 2](#)), the voyage log, passport stamps, and souvenirs were displayed by clicking the icons.

Figure 2 The classification screen for Season 1. When a citizen astronomer clicked on the ship's wheel on the bottom right, a new galaxy was displayed in the centre of the screen. At the same time, three multiple-choice questions appeared below the galaxy in sequence. The three questions correspond to the three steps of the training menu: 1. Spiral or elliptical; 2. Interacting or not interacting; and 3. If interacting, feature(s) of interaction. The icons at the bottom allowed each citizen astronomer to view their personal voyage log and collections, such as souvenirs and passport stamps. Credit: NAOJ

2.1.3 Feature 3: Exploration in one of the world's highest-quality cosmic images The most appealing aspect to citizen astronomers is thought to be Subaru Telescope's HSC-SSP dataset, one of the world's highest-quality cosmic images, taken by the large-aperture Subaru Telescope using the ultra-wide field-of-view camera HSC. Its depth, spatial resolution, and extensive sky coverage stand out. Many interacting features are too faint for small-aperture telescopes to detect, but can be identified by the Subaru Telescope. Galaxy classification with "Subaru quality" images can find new interacting and merging galaxies, as reported by [Tanaka et al. \(2023\)](#), and change researchers' understanding of galaxy evolution. Additionally, the visual experience of identifying distorted galaxies with diverse shapes and discovering faint features is considered attractive to citizen astronomers.

The classification screen of GALAXY CRUISE is based on "hscMap"³, enabling users to easily access the vast HSC-SSP data, similar to Google Maps. For this reason, citizen astronomers can explore cosmic images freely while classifying galaxies, and they sometimes find a galaxy with a unique shape.

In addition to these three features, we created two activities for indirect interactions with citizen astronomers. The first one is a news article on the website, posted on the first day of every month, covering various topics, such as galaxy science, tips for classifying galaxies,

Figure 3 Examples of digital items can be earned during the “Classify 1000 Galaxies in One Month” Campaign. Top: Illustrations of the bronze, silver, and gold medals when citizen astronomers classify 100, 300, and 1000 galaxies during the first campaign from August 1 to 31, 2020. Bottom: The evolution of the snowman illustration when citizen astronomers classify 100, 300, 1000, and 2021 galaxies during the New Year’s campaign from December 12, 2020, to January 11, 2021. Credit: NAOJ

and updates on this project. Some articles are based on questions and reports submitted by citizen astronomers. Additionally, we began featuring reports from astronomy educators and researchers who have incorporated GALAXY CRUISE into their classrooms and hands-on workshops at science museums. We also disseminate information through the X (formerly Twitter) accounts – @Galaxy_Cruise in Japanese and @Galaxy_Cruise_e in English – as well as email newsletters, which are sent approximately four times a year in both Japanese and English. The second one is the “Classify 1000 Galaxies in One Month” campaign, held twice a year in August and the year-end holiday season. During the campaign, an indicator appears on the classification screen, showing each citizen astronomer’s achievements. When citizen astronomers classify a specific number of galaxies, they can earn special digital items that can only be earned during that campaign period (Figure 3). After each campaign, we announce the names of citizen astronomers who have classified more than 1,000 galaxies.

Figure 4 shows enrollment growth in Japan and in other countries and regions. Within two weeks of the Japanese Season 1 site launch on 1 November 2019, 15 articles were published on online news sites, including reprints, and enrollment reached 1,000 participants. By the end of February 2020, enrollment exceeded 1,700, likely due to a feature on the morning news programme, “Ohayo Nippon (Good Morning Japan)”, of the Japan Broadcasting Corporation (NHK) on 21 January 2020. Just after the English site launched on 19 February 2020, online news articles were published in Russia, Canada (in French), Germany, and the United States (e.g., The Washington Post), and more. On 2 March 2020, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, most elementary, junior high, and high schools, as well as special education schools, were temporarily closed throughout Japan. GALAXY CRUISE was introduced across multiple sites as fun science content for kids staying at home, resulting in over 760 enrollments, primarily from teenagers and younger generations. Outside Japan, this project was introduced in

Figure 4 Number of registrants in Japan (blue) and other countries and regions (pink). The Season 1 Japanese site launched on 1 November 2019, and the corresponding English site launched on 19 February 2020. Season 2 launched on 18 April 2022 in both languages, and the Special Campaign for classifying simulated galaxies was held from 12 September 2023 to 1 April 2024. The periods of “Classify 1000 Galaxies in One Month” campaigns are shown in grey. Credit: NAOJ

multiple languages across various countries. As of 15 March 2020, near the beginning of the COVID-19 lockdown in Japan, a total of 3,207 citizen astronomers from 52 countries and regions registered. During some “Classify 1000 Galaxies in One Month” campaigns in August and mid-December to mid-January during Season 1, there was a rapid increase in enrollment. After Season 2 launched, no drastic increase was observed, but the number inside and outside Japan is gradually increasing.

As of 1 August 2025, 14,682 citizen astronomers from 111 countries and regions have registered. The countries with more than 1,000 registrants include Japan (10,005 people), India (1,205), and Malaysia (1,019), followed by the United States (457), Brazil (429), and Russia (411). Over the last five years, we have received media contacts in Japan and identified online articles from both within and outside the Country. When the first peer-reviewed scientific paper (Tanaka et al., 2023) was published in October 2023, more than 15 popular articles, both within and outside Japan, were posted online. As of 1 August 2025, we have detected more than 58 articles related to GALAXY CRUISE, including 16 outside Japan.

3. The study: Evaluation of the project using a user questionnaire

From 1 - 25 July 2021, we conducted a user questionnaire (see Appendix) among registered citizen astronomers to evaluate the features of this project. We announced this survey on our website, X, and in a GALAXY CRUISE email newsletter, in both Japanese and English,

resulting in 261 responses. Out of these, we identified 245 respondents who completed the questionnaire (hereafter, “valid respondents”). The breakdown of these 245 respondents is illustrated in [Figure 5](#), compared to all registrants in GALAXY CRUISE as of 25 July 2021. The ratio of Japanese to foreign respondents was approximately 8:2, while the male-to-female respondent ratio was about 7:3. These ratios were consistent with all registrants. However, in terms of age, we observed that the percentages of respondents in their 10s and 20s were lower, while those aged 50 and above were higher. In fact, around half of the respondents were over 50.

Figure 5 Country (Japan/other countries), gender, and age breakdowns of the respondents (upper row) and all registrants as of July 25, 2021 (lower row). Credit: NAOJ

In the first question, “How often do you participate in classifying galaxies in GALAXY CRUISE?” we asked respondents to select one answer from the following options.

1. I participate regularly before/during/after special campaigns.
2. I participate irregularly, such as only during special campaigns.
3. Currently, I (effectively) do not participate.

Among the 245 valid respondents, those who selected 1 or 2 were categorised as Group A (active users) and were given a 15-question questionnaire. Those who selected three were categorised as Group B respondents (inactive users) and received a separate questionnaire comprising 9 questions, distinct from those given to Group A. Group A was further divided into two subgroups: Group A1 and Group A2. The number of respondents in each group is as follows:

Group A1 (regular active users): 80 respondents who selected 1

Group A2 (irregular active users): 89 respondents who selected 2

Group B (inactive users): 76 respondents who selected 3

This division resulted in a Group A (A1+A2) to Group B ratio of approximately 7:3 (169 to 76).

To identify external motivations for citizen astronomers to participate and to assess the design of this project, we asked Group A active respondents to rate each item on a 5-point Likert Scale for the question, “How much did the following items motivate you?” As shown in [Figure 6](#), “Beautiful images captured by the Subaru Telescope” was rated most positively, followed by “Three (3) training menus to learn about galaxy classification” and “Cosmic voyage-themed welcome page (classification screen).” However, the fourth to seventh items received similar scores to the third one. These items are unique features of GALAXY CRUISE, as explained above. The fourth item is the “Monthly NEWS article,” in which we have featured various topics on the first day of each month since the beginning of this project as the primary source for

Figure 6 Average rating with standard error among Group A respondents, or active users (N=169), on how much each feature of this project motivated them to participate. The ratings are based on a 5-point scale (5 = very much, 4 = much, 3 = a fair amount, 2 = a little, and 1 = not at all/didn't know). The complete phrases are Beautiful images: Beautiful images captured by the Subaru Telescope; Training menus: Three (3) training menus to learn about galaxy classification; Cosmic voyage: Cosmic voyage-themed welcome page (classification screen); NEWS articles: Monthly NEWS articles on the home page; Campaigns: Campaigns with limited-time-only digital items; Messages: Messages from the Captain on the welcome page; Boarding pass: Boarding pass earned after the training menus; Ranking: Rankings showing your nickname; Cabin upgrade: Upgrading your cabin; Passport stamps: Collecting departure stamps on your passport; Screenshot: Screenshot icon to capture your favorite galaxies; Souvenirs: Collecting souvenirs when you complete areas; Tea party: Invitation to a tea party (online gathering) to talk to the Captain; Newsletters: Email Newsletters; Contact form: Asking questions via the contact form; Social media: Twitter (X) and Instagram. Most of the features, except “Tea party,” “newsletters,” and “Social media,” are available on the website. Credit: NAOJ

disseminating information. In this sense, our design for this project is well-suited to motivate the most active users.

We also asked Group A and B respondents to choose their motivations for participating from a list of nine predefined options, plus the “Others” category with an optional comment field. Groups A and B were given different questions: Group A was asked about their ongoing motivations. In contrast, Group B was asked about their initial motivations when they were still classifying galaxies. As our project theme is similar to that of Galaxy Zoo, launched in 2007, we modified the 12 motivation survey categories of [Raddick et al. \(2013\)](#) into nine options in our questionnaire. We included the option “To enjoy the game” to reflect the original elements of GALAXY CRUISE. Additionally, we incorporated “For school classes and/or after-school activities” and “Recommendation by my friends or family” because we observed this project being disseminated as science content during the pandemic. The option “To be involved in citizen science” may seem self-referential, but we included it to assess the awareness of citizen science in Japan, anticipating that most respondents would be Japanese.

As shown in [Figure 7](#), the most selected answer in both groups was “To contribute to astronomy research (hereafter “Contribute”).” However, Group B did not show a significant difference in their percentages from “To learn astronomy (hereafter “Learn”)” and “To see beautiful astronomy images (hereafter “Image”).” In Group A, 80% of respondents selected “Contribute”, more than

Figure 7 Ongoing motivations for participation among Group A active users and initial motivations for Group B inactive users (multiple answers allowed), as selected by the respondents in the questionnaire, are shown as percentages of all respondents in each group. The error bars show standard error. The complete sentences are: Contribute: To contribute to astronomy research; Images: To see beautiful astronomy images; Learn: To learn astronomy; Citizen Science: To be involved in citizen science; Discover: To discover an interesting galaxy; Game: To enjoy the game; Teach: To use the contents as teaching resources; School: For school classes and/or after school activities; Recommended: Recommendation by my friends or family. Credit: NAOJ

Figure 8 The most important motivation to participate in GALAXY CRUISE (only one answer allowed) for Group A, with the standard error. The complete sentences are the same as in Figure 7. Credit: NAOJ

10% higher than in Group B (62%). In addition to this answer, more than 10% more Group A participants chose “Image,” “To be involved in citizen science (hereafter “Citizen Science”),” and “To discover an interesting galaxy (hereafter “Discover”),” compared to Group B. In fact, 24% more Group A participants than Group B participants selected “Citizen Science.” These results indicate that both active and inactive users are motivated to participate in scientific research and work with professionals, but active users show a stronger motivation.

Then, we asked the Group A respondents to select only one reason from the same list as the most important motivation, and almost half selected “Contribute,” making it much more popular than the others (Figure 8). This tendency aligns with Raddick et al. (2013), who found that many respondents of different ages, genders, and educational levels chose “To contribute to scientific research” as their primary reason for participation.

For the Group B inactive respondents, we asked, “Why did you stop participating in GALAXY CRUISE?” As shown in Figure 9, “I am too busy to participate” was the most frequently chosen answer; in this situation, there is nothing we can do to help. However, for the second, third, and fourth most selected responses – “I was not confident in my classification results,” “I was bored,” and “Classifying galaxies was challenging” – there is room for improvement. Among the Group B respondents, 97% expressed interest in participating in GALAXY CRUISE again if given the opportunity. Although they are not currently active, the average satisfaction rating during their participation was 7.1 out of 10, indicating a reasonable level of contentment. The questionnaire results suggest that with our efforts, we may be able to encourage the Group B respondents to rejoin GALAXY CRUISE.

Figure 9 Reasons for stopping participation among Group B inactive users, with standard error, (multiple answers allowed) as a percentage of all respondents in Group B (N=76). The complete sentences are: Too busy: I was too busy to participate; Not confident: I was not confident in my classification results; Bored: I was bored; Challenging: Classifying galaxies was challenging; Satisfied: I was satisfied after trying all the procedures; Hard to operate: Using a smartphone, it was hard to operate; Question(s): I did not solve the question(s) I had; Training menus: The three(3) training menus were not easy; Game elements: The game elements were not exciting; Participation procedure: The participation procedure was hard to understand; Welcome page: How to operate the welcome page (classification screen) was not clear; Completed: I have completed all ten(10) stages; Log in procedure: The log in procedure was not clear; Not fun: Classifying galaxies was not fun; Different: The programme was different from what I expected. Credit: NAOJ

4. Methods: How motivations changed over time

Next, we analysed how the motivations of citizen astronomers to participate in this project changed over time, between when they registered and when they completed the user questionnaire. At registration, we required all citizen astronomers to select their reasons for participation from the same options provided in the questionnaire, except “For school classes and/or after-school activities.” This allowed us to assess how their motivations evolved.

Figure 10 shows motivations for Group A1 (regularly active), Group A2 (irregularly active), and Group B (inactive) at the time of their registration (multiple answers allowed) in comparison to all questionnaire respondents (Groups A1+A2+B) and the overall 6,857 registrants as of 26 July 2021, at the end of the questionnaire period. On 26 July 2021, about 80% of all registrants classified fewer than 100 galaxies, and approximately 20% did not classify any galaxies at all.

Compared to the overall group, Group A1 users displayed a higher motivation to “Contribute” (+23%), “Citizen Science” (+18%), and “Discover” (+10%), while they were less motivated to “enjoy the game (hereafter “Game”)” (-12%). Group A2 users expressed a higher motivation to

Figure 10 Motivations for the Group A1 (regularly active), A2 (irregularly active), and B (inactive) respondents as a percentage with standard error when they registered as citizen astronomers (multiple answers allowed) compared with all questionnaire respondents (Groups A1+A2+B) and the overall registrants as of 26 July 2021. The complete sentences are the same as in Figure 7. Credit: NAOJ

“Contribute” (+15%), “Citizen Science” (+9%), and “Images” (+7%). Meanwhile, Group B users demonstrated a higher motivation in “Contribute” (+8%) and “Learn” (+8%). All three groups combined showed greater motivation to “Contribute” at registration, as indicated by the purple bar.

Figure 11 shows the changes in motivations at the time of registration (“as before”) compared to the questionnaire conducted in July 2021 (“as after”). Each respondent had a different duration of participation; some joined shortly after the launch in November 2019, while others joined a few days before the questionnaire was administered. Nevertheless, we assessed how the motivations of citizen astronomers evolved within each group. The fourth graph shows the percentage differences in motivations before and after for each group. In the active groups (A1 and A2), “Contribute” was one of the primary motivations. For Group A1, “Contribute” was the top motivation at 67.5% when they registered, while in Group A2, it was as high as “Learn” (~60%). The percentage of respondents in both Group A1 and A2 selecting “Contribute” increased in the questionnaire.

In contrast, more respondents in Group B initially selected “Learn” (63.2%) than “Contribute” (52.6%), and the growth rate for “Contribute” was lower than that of Groups A1 and A2. When comparing the three groups, the more active group demonstrated a higher Contribute/Learn ratio from the beginning, as shown in Table 1.

In addition to “Contribute”, there was an increase in the percentages for “Images,” “Citizen Science,” and “Discover” in Groups A1 and A2. Notably, in Group A1, the “Images” option saw a significant 36.3% increase, indicating the appeal of the beautiful images captured by the

Figure 11 Reasons for registering to GALAXY CRUISE (“Before”) and when responding to the questionnaire (“After”) for a) Groups A1 (regularly active), b) A2 (irregularly active), and c) B (inactive), with d) the change in percentages between “Before” and “After.” Respondents were allowed to choose multiple answers. Credit: NAOJ

Subaru Telescope. This finding aligns with the observation that active users rated “Beautiful images captured by the Subaru Telescope” the highest motivation for participation (Figure 6). Interestingly, even “Game,” one of the minor motivations, increased in Group A1, while it decreased in Groups A2 and B. Due to the different definitions, we cannot directly compare the studies by Gugliucci et al. (2021); however, the trend in their paper that “Persisters”, who participate on a more regular basis, have more reasons than “dabblers” who participate on a more sporadic basis, looks similar to our results.

	Before			After		
	Contribute	Learn	C/L	Contribute	Learn	C/L
Group A1	67.5%	56.3%	1.2	82.5%	58.8%	1.4
Group A2	59.6%	60.7%	1.0	78.7%	64.0%	1.2
Group B	52.6%	63.2%	0.8	61.8%	61.8%	1.0

Table 1 Percentages of “Contribute” and “Learn” chosen in Groups A1, A2, and B at registration (Before) and questionnaire (After) with the Contribute/Learn (C/L) ratio. Credit: NAOJ

The more active the group, the more reasons they had for their choices, resulting in a higher percentage increase. Figure 12 shows the histogram displaying the number of reasons each astronomer chose at registration (as “Before”) and at the questionnaire (as “After”) in each group. The average number of reasons increased for all groups: +0.9, +0.7, and +0.2 points in the mean for Groups A1, A2, and B, respectively.

Figure 12 Histograms displaying the number of reasons each citizen astronomer chose at registration (as “Before”) and at the questionnaire (as “After”) in each group. The arrows labeled “B” and “A” represent the mean number of reasons for “Before” and “After” for each group, respectively. Credit: NAOJ

Figure 13 Four categories of citizen astronomers based on their self-evaluation using a four-point scale: “A) Authentic Astronomy Enthusiasts” who prefer more academic topics and dedicate a longer time to astronomy and outer space. “B) Potential Astronomy Enthusiasts” who prefer academic topics and spend less time on astronomy. “C) Light Astronomy Lovers” who prefer more casual topics and spend a longer time in astronomy. “D) Those with Little Interest” who prefer casual topics and spend a shorter time in astronomy. Credit: NAOJ

5. Findings: Changes in active users' characteristics

Along with reasons to participate, we asked citizen astronomers to evaluate their attitudes and preferences toward learning about astronomy and outer space, as well as the time they spend on these subjects. We used a four-point scale both at registration and in the questionnaire to gather information about their characteristics using our unique method. For attitude, a rating of 1 indicates a more casual interest, while a rating of 4 signifies a more academic focus. Similarly, for time spent, a rating of 1 represents the shortest time and a rating of 4 the longest. Based on their self-evaluations, we categorised users into four groups according to their characteristics: "A) Authentic Astronomy Enthusiasts", "B) Potential Astronomy Enthusiasts",

Figure 14 The portion of the four categories, comparing when citizen astronomers registered for GALAXY CRUISE (as "Before") and when they responded to the questionnaire (as "After"), for Groups A1 (top), A2 (middle), and B (bottom). The four categories are A) Authentic Astronomy Enthusiasts, B) Potential Astronomy Enthusiasts, C) Light Astronomy Lovers, and D) Those with Little Interest. Credit: NAOJ

"C) Light Astronomy Lovers", and "D) Those with Little Interest". (Figure 13).

GALAXY CRUISE was designed to target "A) Authentic Astronomy Enthusiasts". However, as shown in Figure 14, when citizen astronomers registered, more than half of the participants in Groups A1, A2, and B were "D) Those with Little Interest". Only 22.5% of users in Group A1 were "A) Authentic Astronomy Enthusiasts". The results from the questionnaire show that the percentage of "A) Authentic Astronomy Enthusiasts" did not change drastically over time in Groups A2 and B. In contrast, in Group A1, "D) Those with Little Interest" decreased by 21.2%, while "A) Authentic Astronomy Enthusiasts" increased by 20.0%. Group A1 users regularly

classified galaxies for multiple reasons, including contributing to astronomy research, enjoying the beauty of astronomical images, and engaging in citizen science. As a result, they were able to spend more time on astronomy and shifted their preference towards more academic topics. These results demonstrate that we successfully attracted new astronomy enthusiasts through the citizen science project.

6. After the study: Latest activities

In the questionnaire conducted in July 2021, we asked respondents in both Groups A and B to rate our activities so far and future attempts on a 5-point scale, identifying which aspects would attract Group A to participate in Season 2 and Group B to return. As presented in [Figure 15](#), both groups rated “Streaming videos of a researcher explaining scientific results” most positively. Considering the results, we started an irregular livestream on the Subaru Telescope YouTube channels (@SubaruTelescopeNAOJ in Japanese and @SubaruTelescopeNAOJe in English).

The first live classification of galaxies was streamed on 23 December 2022, in Japanese and on 29 August 2023, in English. This initiative aimed to familiarise inactive users with classifying

Figure 15 Average ratings by Group A (active) respondents on how motivating each item is for participation in Season 2, and by Group B (inactive) respondents on how motivating each item is for renewed participation. The ratings are based on a 5-point scale (5 = very much, 4 = much, 3 = a fair amount, 2 = a little, and 1 = not at all). The complete sentences are: Streaming videos: Streaming videos of a researcher explaining scientific results; Physical gifts: Campaigns with physical gifts; Digital items: Campaigns with limited-time-only digital items; New story: The beginning of a new story; Meet the Captain: Events to meet the Captain and the bridge crew members; Inquiry contact: Inquiry contact for asking questions quickly; Online forum: An online forum to discuss among Citizen Astronomers; Game elements: Addition of game elements. Credit: NAOJ

galaxies and encourage them to return to it. As of October 2024, we have conducted six live streams in Japanese and four in English. On 10 November 2023, “Captain” Masayuki Tanaka presented the highlights of the first published scientific paper ([Tanaka et al., 2023](#)) and expressed his gratitude to the citizen astronomers. Additionally, on 26 July 2024, “Navigator” Makoto Ando shared preliminary results from the scientific analysis of the 2023 Special Campaign, during which citizen astronomers classified simulated galaxies. The average number of viewers during live sessions is relatively low, with 51 in Japanese and 13 in English on average; however, it gradually increases after the stream, with an average of ~400 views in Japanese and ~140 in English.

After the live stream on 21 April 2023, a citizen astronomer posted a comment on the Subaru Telescope YouTube channel saying, “Good evening. I once tried to classify galaxies, but it was too challenging, so I gave up. This time, while watching the live classification, I felt like I could tackle it a bit. It seems difficult even for experts, so I realised that it’s natural for a beginner to struggle.” ([Tamenishiki, 2023](#); translation from the original Japanese by author). This comment highlights the potential of live classification sessions to support citizen astronomers who lack confidence in their classifications and wish to restart their participation.

As described in the section “About GALAXY CRUISE: Unique Features,” we, the bridge crew members, have worked to communicate indirectly with citizen astronomers through news articles, email newsletters, and social media. Recently, we started live streaming to promote more active interaction. Additionally, we organised two direct communication events with citizen astronomers. We held the first “Shipboard Tea Party” online event on 20 June and 27 June 2021, during the COVID-19 pandemic period. For the regular tea party on 27 June, we selected 18 citizen astronomers by lottery from those who classified more than 100 galaxies during a specified period, and 12 attended. We also invited 23 top-rankers in galaxy classification for a special event on 20 June, of which eight joined. During the online tea parties, Captain Tanaka presented updates on scientific analysis, followed by a question-and-answer session with the participants. We received numerous questions and requests regarding GALAXY CRUISE.

The second event, “Social Event with Citizen Astronomers,” was held on the third day of “The Violent Universe” science meeting, with the theme of interacting and merging galaxies, a topic most GALAXY CRUISE bridge crew members planned and organised. The Violent Universe became the first NAOJ science meeting to combine science sessions with a social gathering with citizen astronomers. The three-day meeting was designed in a hybrid format, with onsite sessions at NAOJ headquarters in Mitaka, Tokyo, Japan, and online sessions.

During a hybrid social event on 28 September 2024, nine onsite and seven online citizen astronomers participated. In the morning, eleven researchers who attended the science sessions joined the social event to give short talks or speak at a science café. They presented their research and scientific interests in an accessible manner, connecting their work with GALAXY CRUISE. Citizen astronomers, especially onsite participants, were highly engaged,

asking numerous questions and talking to researchers. The enthusiasm of participants in communicating with the researchers is thought to be consistent with the changes in the characteristics of Group A1 users, as shown in [Figure 14](#). The afternoon session began with the GALAXY CRUISE science highlights presented by the science team. At the following citizen astronomer session, “GALAXY CRUISE and Me,” two citizen astronomers shared their stories about how to get started and enjoy classifying galaxies. Participants and bridge crew members empathised with their experiences. The social event provided researchers and citizen astronomers a unique opportunity to meet with their common scientific interests, leading to engaging and in-depth discussions. The report of this social event was published as a GALAXY CRUISE NEWS article on 1 November 2024.

7. Conclusion

Using big observational data, we designed and promoted the first citizen science project in Japan: GALAXY CRUISE. We developed the website in Japanese and English with unique features like the three-step training menu that provides simple but effective steps for citizen science beginners to become familiar with galaxy classification and feel comfortable to participate, the voyaging-themed world and gamification events that keep engaging citizen astronomers to classify galaxies, and the welcome page (classification screen) to explore the vast and beautiful cosmic images captured by the Subaru Telescope. We share helpful scientific information and updates, such as news articles on the website, social media posts, and email newsletters, to reach out to citizen astronomers about our activities. The results of the user questionnaire conducted in July 2021 showed that the training modules and the beautiful images from the Subaru Telescope were two of the most important features (and two of the three unique features of GALAXY CRUISE) that effectively kept citizen astronomers engaged ([Figure 6](#)). The questionnaire analysis also revealed the following findings.

- The primary reason for participating in GALAXY CRUISE is to contribute to astronomy research, particularly for active users ([Figure 7](#)). Nearly half of active users identified contribution to research as their most significant motivation for participating ([Figure 8](#)).
- The active user groups are highly motivated from the beginning to contribute to astronomy research ([Figure 10](#)). As they continue to participate, they develop additional motivations, such as viewing beautiful images, discovering interesting galaxies, and even enjoying the game ([Figure 11](#)).
- In contrast, to learn about astronomy was the top reason for currently inactive users when they registered ([Figure 10](#)), and the growth rate of “to contribute” was lower than that of active users ([Figure 11](#)). The ratio of “to contribute” over “to learn” ([Table 1](#)) may be an indicator of how actively GALAXY CRUISE citizen astronomers continue to participate.

· The characteristics of regularly active users changed over time; they came to spend more time engaging with astronomy and have developed an interest in academic astronomy content (Figure 14). As a citizen or participatory science project in astronomy, GALAXY CRUISE is thought to be successful in fostering genuine enthusiasm for astronomy.

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Notes

1. GALAXY CRUISE: <https://galaxycruise.mtk.nao.ac.jp/en/>
2. The Illustris TNG Project: <https://www.tng-project.org>
3. hscMap: <http://hscmap.mtk.nao.ac.jp/hscMap4/>

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Appendix

Appendix A: Complete Survey

Start of Block Participation Criterion

How often do you participate (classify galaxies) in GALAXY CRUISE?

- I participate regularly before/during/after special campaigns.
- I participate irregularly, such as only during special campaigns.
- Currently, I (effectively) do not participate.

Skip to *Block Questionnaire A (for active users)* if respondent answers “I participate regularly before/during/after special campaigns.” or “I participate irregularly, such as only during special campaigns.” to this question.

Skip to *Block Questionnaire B (for inactive users)* if respondent answers “Currently, I (effectively) do not participate.” to this question.

End of Block Participation Criterion

Start of Block Questionnaire A (for active users)

What are the reasons you participate in GALAXY CRUISE? (Multi answers allowed)

- To contribute to astronomy research
- To learn astronomy
- To enjoy the game
- To see beautiful astronomy images
- To use the contents as teaching resources
- To discover an interesting galaxy
- To be involved in citizen science
- Recommendation by my friends or family
- For school classes and/or after school activities
- Others (write comments)

What is the most important reason you participate in GALAXY CRUISE? (Select one)

- To contribute to astronomy research
- To learn astronomy
- To enjoy the game
- To see beautiful astronomy images
- To use the contents as teaching resources
- To discover an interesting galaxy
- To be involved in citizen science

- Recommendation by my friends or family
- For school classes and/or after school activities
- Others (write comments)

When do you participate in GALAXY CRUISE? (Multi answers allowed)

- Weekdays, 0:00-6:00
- Weekdays, 6:00-12:00
- Weekdays, 12:00-18:00
- Weekdays, 18:00-24:00
- Weekends, 0:00-6:00
- Weekends, 6:00-12:00
- Weekends, 12:00-18:00
- Weekends, 18:00-24:00

From which location(s) do you participate in GALAXY CRUISE? (Multi answers allowed)

- Home
- In transit (when going to work/school)
- Workplace/School
- Public facilities such as libraries
- Restaurants and/or Cafes
- Others (write comments)

Which device(s) do you use to participate in GALAXY CRUISE? (Multi answers allowed)

- Desktop PC
- Laptop (Notebook PC)
- Tablet
- Smartphone
- Others (write comments)

Which device do you use the most to participate? (Select one)

- Desktop PC
- Laptop (Notebook PC)
- Tablet
- Smartphone
- Others (write comments)

How often do you access the following media? Please select one of: "almost everyday", "once-twice a week", "once-twice a month", and "almost never"

- GALAXY CRUISE Website
- GALAXY CRUISE Twitter
- GALAXY CRUISE Instagram

GALAXY CRUISE E-mail Newsletter

How much did the following items motivate you? The rating varies from “not at all” (1) to “very much” (5). Select the most appropriate grade between 1 and 5.

- Three(3) training menus to learn about galaxy classification
- Boarding Pass earned after the training menus
- Cosmic Voyage themed Welcome Page
- Beautiful images captured by the Subaru Telescope
- Screenshot icon to capture your favourite galaxies
- Collecting souvenirs when you complete areas
- Collecting departure stamps on your passport
- Upgrading your cabin
- Rankings showing your nickname
- Messages from the Captain on the Welcome Page
- Campaigns with limited-time-only digital items
- Invitation to a tea party to talk to the Captain
- News articles
- Twitter and Instagram
- E-mail Newsletters
- Asking questions via the contact form

What motivates you to login again? (Multi answers allowed)

- Messages from the Captain on the Welcome Page
- E-mail Newsletters
- Monthly NEWS articles on the home page
- GALAXY CRUISE social media accounts
- Other social media accounts
- Recommendations by schools and/or after school programs
- Others (write comments)
- None of the above

Continue to *Block About the Ongoing SEASON 1*.

Start of Block About the Ongoing SEASON 1

Respond to the following questions by selecting the most appropriate grade between 1 and 5. The rating varies from “not at all” (1) to “very much” (5).

How easy to understand was the participation preparation procedure (learning the basic knowledge, earning the Boarding Pass, and then boarding the cruise ship)?

How easy is the welcome page to operate for classifying galaxies and using icons?

How much was your interest in interacting galaxies increased after you participated in GALAXY CRUISE?

Would you recommend GALAXY CRUISE to your friends? The rating varies from “not at all” (1) to “Yes, definitely” (10). Select the most appropriate grade between 1 and 10.

End of Block About the Ongoing SEASON 1

Continue to *Block About the Upcoming SEASON 2*.

Start of Block About the Upcoming SEASON 2

How attractive are the following items for you? The rating varies from “not at all” (1) to “very much” (5). Select the most appropriate grade between 1 and 5.

- Campaigns with limited-time-only digital items
- Campaigns with physical gifts
- Streaming videos of a researcher explaining scientific results
- Events to meet the Captain and the bridge crew members
- An online forum to discuss among Citizen Astronomers
- Addition of game elements
- The beginning of a new story
- Inquiry contact for asking questions quickly

Please share your ideas and requests for new functions and communication tools (if any).

End of Block About the Upcoming SEASON 2

At the end of *Block Questionnaire A (for active users)*, proceed to *Block Common Questions*.

End of Block Questionnaire A (for active users)

Start of Block Questionnaire B (for inactive users)

Why did you stop participating in GALAXY CRUISE? (Multi answers allowed)

- The participation procedure was hard to understand.
- The three(3) training menus were not easy.
- The log in procedure was not clear.
- Classifying galaxies was challenging.
- I was not confident in my classification results.
- Classifying galaxies was not fun.
- The game elements were not exciting.

-
- I was bored.
 - I am too busy to participate.
 - Using a smartphone, it was hard to operate.
 - I did not answer the question(s) I had.
 - The program was different from what I expected.
 - I have completed all ten(10) stages.
 - I was satisfied after trying all the procedures.
 - Others (write comments)

Which of the following items describe you? (Multi answers allowed)

- I completed all three(3) training menus (Lessons 1, 2, 3).
- I tried the "Practice Course" on the welcome page.
- I classified galaxies in Stage 1.
- I received departure stamp(s) on the passport.
- I classified galaxies in Stage 2.
- I classified galaxies in Stage 3.
- I classified galaxies in Stage 4.
- I classified galaxies in Stage 5 (and possibly higher stages)
- I participated in campaign(s).
- I obtained limited-time-only digital item(s) through campaign(s).
- None of the above.

What are the initial reasons you participated in GALAXY CRUISE? (Multi answers allowed)

- To contribute to astronomy research
- To learn astronomy
- To enjoy the game
- To see beautiful astronomy images
- To use the contents as teaching resources
- To discover an interesting galaxy
- To be involved in citizen science
- Recommendation by my friends or family
- For school classes and/or after school activities
- Others (write comments)

Have the initial reasons for your participation been satisfied? The rating varies from "Not at all" (1) to "very much" (10). Select the most appropriate grade between 1 and 10.

Which of the following items/events do you know about? (Multi answers allowed)

- Messages from the Captain on the Welcome Page
- E-mail Newsletters

-
- Monthly NEWS articles on the home page
 - Campaigns with limited-time-only digital items
 - Twitter and Instagram introducing interesting galaxies
 - None of the above

How often do you access the following? For each entry, select one of the following: "often", "sometimes", "rarely" and "never".

- GALAXY CRUISE Website
- GALAXY CRUISE Twitter
- GALAXY CRUISE Instagram
- GALAXY CRUISE E-mail Newsletter

Please share your ideas and requests for new functions and communication tools (if any).

Would you like to participate in GALAXY CRUISE again if you have a chance?

- Yes
- No

If the respondent answers "No" to the question, Would you like to participate in GALAXY CRUISE again if you have a chance?, continue to Block Common Questions.

If the respondent answers "Yes" to the question, Would you like to participate in GALAXY CRUISE again if you have a chance?, display the following question:

How likely are the following items to motivate you to participate again? The rating varies from "not at all" (1) to "very much" (5). Select the most appropriate grade between 1 and 5.

- Campaigns with limited-time-only digital items
- Campaigns with physical gifts
- Streaming videos of a researcher explaining scientific results
- Events to meet the Captain and the bridge crew members
- An online forum to discuss among Citizen Astronomers
- Addition of game elements
- The beginning of a new story
- Inquiry contact for asking questions quickly

At the end of Block Questionnaire B (for inactive users), proceed to Block Common Questions.

End of Block Questionnaire B (for inactive users)

Start of Block Common Questions

On a scale from 1 to 4, where 1 is “more enjoyable” and 4 is “more academic”, what is your preference for learning about astronomy or outer space?

On a scale from 1 to 4, where 1 is “shortest” and 4 is “longest”, how much time do you spend on astronomy or outer space?

Location where you live (If you live in Japan, please select one prefecture. If not, select “outside of Japan”)

- In Japan
 Select prefecture
- Outside of Japan

Gender (Select one.)

- Man
- Woman
- Other

Age (Select one.)

- Younger than 10
- 10s
- 20s
- 30s
- 40s
- 50s
- 60s
- 70s
- 80s+

Housemate(s) (Multi answers allowed)

- Spouse or partner
- Child(ren)
- Grandchild(ren)
- Parent(s) and/or Parent(s) in-law
- Others
- Live alone

End of Block Common Questions